

Spectrophotometric Studies of Rhenium Complexes with 1-Phenyl-2, 4-Dithiobiuret[†]

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The microcrystalline reagent, 1-Phenyl-2, 4-dithiobiuret, forms a stable brownish-yellow complex with rhenium on reducing it with stannous chloride in 2*N* to 3*N* hydrochloric acid medium and the metal can be estimated in 50 percent aqueous *N,N*-dimethyl formamide (DMF) solvent system. The system obeys Beer's law from 1-16 p.p.m. from 390-420 nm. The molar absorptivity is $[9.3 \pm 0.25] \times 10^3$ at 390 nm and the Sandell's sensitivity is 0.0195 μg of Re per cm^2 . The metal forms a 1 : 2 complex (metal to ligand) with the ligand. The probable chelation reaction has been proposed, showing that one ligand is in the outer sphere while the other forms inner sphere complex. This has been well explained by equilibrium constants data.

In spite of the wide application of the sulphur bearing ligands in analytical chemistry, only very few sensitive and selective reagents have been used for determination of rhenium 6-chloro-8-mercaptoquinoline¹ ($\epsilon = 1.14 \times 10^4$), Unithiol² ($\epsilon = 3.69 \times 10^3$), diethyl dithio-phosphoric acid³ ($\epsilon = 6.2 \times 10^2$), thiosalicylic acid⁴ ($\epsilon = 6.1 \times 10^3$), thioglycolic acid⁵ ($\epsilon = 3.6 \times 10^3$) and toluene-3, 4-dithiol⁶ ($\epsilon = 2.34 \times 10^4$) are some of the colour forming thioligands utilized in spectrophotometric determination of rhenium. Of these 6-chloro-8-mercaptoquinoline has been proved to be useful reagent for extraction and estimation. The reagent dithiol⁶, has a reasonable degree of precision and sensitivity, but has interference from Cu, Ni, Co, Pt, W and Mo. The method is very much time consuming. Except for thiosalicylic acid, no data regarding composition of the complex, and also no work has been done up to date to ascertain the stepwise stability data of rhenium complexes.

The present work describes the sensitive colour reaction of 1-Phenyl-2, 4-dithiobiuret with ReO_4^- in presence of Sn^{2+} and 2-3*N* HCl in 50 percent aqueous-DMF solvent medium. The metal forms 1:2 complex as determined by Job's and molar ratio methods. The equilibrium constants have been evaluated by extending Leden's and Rossotti-Rossotti's method by graphical extrapolation using spectrophotometric data. In light of the experimental data a probable reaction route has been proposed.

Experimental

All the spectral measurements were carried out with the Hilger-UVispek spectrophotometer using matched 1 cm glass cells.

Reagents :

Standard solution of rhenium was prepared by

dissolving K ReO_4 (Jhonson & Mathey, 99.9% pure) in double distilled water, containing 1.00 mg of Re per ml. Desired solutions were prepared by proper dilution of the stock solutions. The acidity of the system was adjusted with concentrated HCl (A.R.).

N,N-dimethyl formamide was purified by refluxing it over KOH for 7-8 hrs, followed by distillation. The reagent, 1-Phenyl 2, 4-dithiobiuret (obtained from Lederle Laboratories, U.S.A.) was used without further purification. A freshly prepared (0.1% w/v) DMF solution of the microcrystalline reagent was used for the spectrophotometric studies.

Recommended procedure :

To an appropriate aliquot of the test solution containing 0.1 mg to 0.4 mg of rhenium in 25 ml volumetric flask, add 5.1 ml of concentrated HCl followed by 7.5 ml of DMF and let it cool to room temperature ($28 \pm 2^\circ$). Then add 1 ml of 0.5 percent reagent solution followed by 1.0 ml of 23.2% of SnCl_2 . The volume was made up with twice distilled water. After thorough mixing it was cooled to room temperature and solutions were measured at 390 nm after 1.5 hr. against solvent blank.

Choice of the solvent :

The reagent itself is very sparingly soluble in non-polar solvents such as chloroform, benzene and also in oxygenated solvents such as iso-amyl alcohol, ethyl acetate etc. Though it is soluble in acetone and acetonitrile, it is highly soluble in DMF. It has been observed that when DMF present is less than 40 percent, the solution gets turbid. Therefore all the study was made in 50 percent aqueous-DMF solvent system.

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Results and Discussion

Absorbance Spectra :

The absorption spectra of solutions of rhenium-1-phenyl-2, 4-dithiobiuret ($Re=2.1482 \times 10^{-5}M$ and $Re=4.2964 \times 10^{-5}M$) in the said solvent and at 2.5N HCl, prepared according to the recommended procedure were studied from 250 nm to 550nm. The reagent blank has no absorbance at 370 nm and onwards. No peak was observed in the visible region of the spectra and the absorbance of the complex gradually decreases as the wavelength decreases. The optimum wavelength is 390 nm, where other spectral studies are performed.

Effect of variables :

It was been found that the order of addition is not important except that the $SnCl_2$ must be added last. Low results were obtained if the reagent was added last because of the formation of Re^{4+} . It has been observed that 2.0 ml of 5.8% $SnCl_2$ (in 1 N HCl) were sufficient for full colour development. There was no change in the absorbance upto 10 ml of $SnCl_2$ solution. For all subsequent measurements, 1 ml of 23.2% of $SnCl_2$ were used.

For maximum colour development, 2-3N HCl medium is required. Below 1N HCl the solution becomes turbid and at higher normality (above 3N HCl) the absorbance gradually decreases.

The study of the reagent concentration with different quantities (1 to 10 ml) of reagent solutions added to 8 p. p. m. of rhenium indicates that 5ml of 0.1% reagent was sufficient, since there is no appreciable change in absorbance from 2 ml to 10 ml of reagent solution.

The absorbance changes with time under the recommended conditions. The colour reaction is complete in 50 min. and is stable for at least 8 hrs. at room temperature ($28 \pm 2^\circ$).

Beer's Law, Sensitivity, Optimum range :

Test solutions with different concentrations of rhenium were prepared by the recommended procedure. The system adheres to Beer's law from 1 to 16 ppm. from 390—420 nm. It does not obey the law at 370—380nm.

The molar absorptivity as obtained from Beer's law is $[9.3 \pm 0.25] \times 10^3$ at 390 nm and Sandell's sensitivity is 0.0195 μg of rhenium per cm^2 .

The Ringbom's optimal concentration range for measurement was found to be from 3-16 p.p.m of Re^{7+} .

Effect of diverse ions :

The effect of diverse ions on the rhenium deter-

mination was studied by adding 400 p.p.m. of the ion in question to a solution containing 8 p.p.m. of rhenium as ReO_4^- and proceeding as in recommended procedure. Except for molybdenum, copper, and osmium, the method is free from interferences. The molybdenum interference can be removed by ethyl xanthate—extraction⁷. The results are summarized in the following Table 1.

Composition of the complex :

Determination of the ligand to metal ratio were carried out by the method of Job and found to be reproducible at different ReO_4^- concentrations. Equimolar solutions ($1.0741 \times 10^{-5}M$) of the metal ion and reagent were mixed in complementary proportions of 6 ml and 12ml, final volume being 25 ml. The metal to ligand ratio is found to be 1 : 2.

Ions	Amount Tolerated p.p.m.	Ions	Amount tolerated p.p.m.
V^{5+}	100	CH_3COO^-	800
Fe^{3+}	400	EDTA	800
Fe^{2+}	400	Tartrate	800
Ni^{2+}	400	Oxalate	800
Cr^{3+}	200	SO_4^{2-}	800
Mn^{2+}	400	PO_4^{3-}	800
Co^{2+}	12	F^-	800
Cu^{2+}	SI^*	NO_3^-	800
Mo^{6+}	SI^*	SCN^-	800
W^{6+}	320	Citrate	800
Cd^{2+}	400	SI^*	„Seriously interfere
Pd^{2+} , Pt^{4+}	SI^*		do
OS^{8+}	SI^*		do

The composition was further verified by molar ratio method. For a constant metal ion concentration $4.2964 \times 10^{-5}M$, a plot of absorbance against increasing ligand concentration gave a break metal to ligand ratio of 1 : 2.

Step-Wise Formation Constants

The procedure for evaluation of the stepwise formation constants was examined by proper extension of Leden's method^{8, 10} and verified by the method of Rossotti and Rossotti⁹.

Leden's method :

For evaluation of k_1 and k_2 we have assumed that the equilibrium concentrations of the ligand is equal to the total ligand concentrations. This assumption is found to be valid as is evident from the values of free ligand concentrations, calculated for each determination of absorbances.

The successive stability values obtained by considering the degree of complexation are given below—

$$\lim_{L \rightarrow 0} \psi_1 = \lim_{L \rightarrow 0} \frac{\phi - 1}{L} = \beta_1$$

The plot of ψ_1 against free ligand concentration gave a straight line of intercept $\beta_1 = 1.04 \times 10^5$ and a negative slope (β_2 to be negative) on extrapolation to $L \rightarrow 0$ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Subsidiary function of ψ_1 as function of L

Similarly by substituting the value of β_1 in the following function

$$\lim_{L \rightarrow 0} \phi_2 = \lim_{L \rightarrow 0} \frac{\phi_1 - \beta_1}{L} = \beta_2 = -7.10^9$$

Since β_2 has been obtained to be negative, it can be suggested that the second ligand is not bound to rhenium atom directly.

Rossotti and Rossotti's Method :

This method is based on the absorbance of a complex dependent on the total concentrations of ligand and central group¹¹. When only the two complexes are formed, then β_1 and β_2 may be calculated from the following equations.

$$\epsilon = \frac{As - \epsilon_1 L}{C_M L} = \frac{\epsilon_0 + \epsilon_1 \beta_1 L}{1 + \beta_1 L} \quad (i)$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{As - \epsilon_1 L}{C_M L} = \frac{\epsilon_0 + \epsilon_1 \beta_1 L + \epsilon_2 \beta_2 L^2}{1 + \beta_1 L + \beta_2 L^2} \quad (ii)$$

The plot of ϵ against $\frac{\epsilon - \epsilon_0}{L}$ gave a straight line of slope $-\beta_1$ and of intercept ϵ_1 for the complex.

Fig. 2 Plot of β_1 by Rossotti-Rossotti's method

The values of β_1 and ϵ_1 are found to be (Fig. 2).

$$\beta_1 = 1.304 \times 10^5$$

$$\epsilon_1 = 8.350 \times 10^3$$

These values of β_1 and ϵ_1 were further substituted in equation (ii) which was solved as below.

$$\frac{\epsilon_0 - \epsilon}{\epsilon L^2} + \frac{(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon)\beta_1}{\epsilon L} = \beta_2 - \frac{\epsilon_2 \beta_2}{\epsilon} \quad (iii)$$

and values of $-\epsilon_2 \beta_2$ and β_2 were obtained as the slope and intercept, respectively, of the linear plot of the left hand side of equation (iii) against ϵ^{-1} . The values of β_2 and ϵ_2 are :

$$\beta_2 = 2.62 \times 10^8$$

$$\epsilon_2 = 9.04 \times 10^3$$

The value of molar extinction co-efficient mentioned before, obtained from Beer's law, $\epsilon = (9.3 \pm 0.25) \times 10^3$ shows a close resemblance with the value obtained from graphical extrapolation, $\epsilon_2 = 9.04 \times 10^3$. Since ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 values are slightly different, the two ligands may be linked with the metal in different ways. The values of k_1 and k_2 are given below :

$$k_1 = 1.304 \times 10^5$$

$$k_2 = 2.009 \times 10^3$$

Thus it may be suggested that the first ligand forms inner-sphere complex with rhenium (5^+) through the two sulphur atoms, and the second ligand is utilised in forming an ion-pair complex in the outer sphere with the resultant chelate obtained from 1 : 1 ligand to metal interaction.

The coloured Re-complex was found to be absorbed by anionic, but not by cationic, exchange resins suggesting the complex is negatively charged. It can be suggested that the oxidation state of rhenium in this complex is 5^+ , because on addition of ligand after reduction of ReO_4^- with SnCl_2 gave low results which may be attributed to the formation of $\text{Re} (4^+)$ along with $\text{Re} (5^+)$, whereas Re^{4+} is inactive towards this ligand. The Re^{4+} sulphate complex was prepared and was further treated with

the ligand in DMF. No change in spectra occurred when it was compared with the spectra of rhenium-(4⁺)-sulphate. Also the acetone solution of the ligand was treated with k₂ReCl₆ and refluxed for 2 hrs. No complex was formed. Thus it can be concluded that rhenium is in oxidation state 5⁺.

Since the reaction has been carried out in higher acidity range (2.5N HCl), the ligand will get protonated through one of the nitrogen atom which will act as cation to form ion-pair complex with the resultant anionic species obtained from 1:1 interaction.

Overall stability constant :

The overall stability constant was also calculated by Harvey and Manning method¹² using Job's and Beer's law data considering the degree of dissociation α.

The value of overall stability constant calculated from above method is nearly the same as obtained from Rossotti-Rossotti's method for β₂. All the results are given in Table 2.

Table-2

Stability constants of rhenium-biuret complex at (28±2)°

Method	k ₁	k ₂	β ₂ = K	Average K
Leden's	1.04 x 10 ⁶	-ive	-	2.76 x 10 ⁸
Rossotti-Rossotti's	1.304 x 10 ⁶	2.0 x 10 ⁸	2.62 x 10 ⁸	
Harvey & Manning's	—	—	2.90 x 10 ⁸	

Thus in the light of above experimental results and discussion it can be suggested that the following

equilibrium reaction exist in the 53% aqueous—non-aqueous media.

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